

paper Chain

Guidelines for the implementation of
the Circular Economy models.

FACTSHEET CC1b

GLDs and Grits containing Asphalt pavements

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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Keywords

Guidelines	Construction material	Pulp & Paper Industry (PPI)	Circular Economy Model (CEM)	Fact sheet
assessment	requirement	standard	Waste	performance
Asphalt	Pavement	Grits	GLDs	mixtures

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CC1b – GLDs and Grits containing Asphalt pavements.

CC1b: GLDs and Grits in Asphalt pavements: GLDs and Grits can replace partially standard fillers and aggregates in the production of asphalt pavements. Circular Case 1b is focused on the use of treated Grits and Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) as fillers and aggregates on the elaboration of a bituminous mixture of type AC 14 on a road surface layer in an industrial site, substituting standard raw materials: 1) standard bituminous mixture, 2) section with fine aggregates were partially replaced by grits, 3) section where the fine aggregates were partially replaced by GLD, and 4) section where the fine aggregates were partially replaced by grits and GLDs. Waste pre-treatment consisting on drying, sieving, and, also salts washing. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements. CC1b CEM has a high replicability potential. THE NAVIGATOR COMPANY (PPI) produced GLDs and grits wastes were managed by DILUMEX carrying out the material transportation and waste pre-treatment. Elaboration of the asphalt mixture by MEGAVIA (Constructor). UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO (UAVR) collaborated with DILUMEX and NAVIGATOR in this Circular Case, for technical support. Figure 1 shows the CC1 Circular Case in Portugal integrating the CC1a (see factsheet CC1a), and CC1b, Figures 2 to 4 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration, and Tables 1 and 2 show CC main items, key factors and lessons learnt.

CC1b (Asphalts based on Grits and GLDs) Guidelines:

- ✚ Circular Economy Models using Grits and Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs) as aggregates in asphalt road pavements as developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC1b), are basically limited by its classification as "waste", the lack of specific legal framework promoting their use, and extra cost coming from their treatment based on salts removal, drying and sieving. Technical and environmental performance and workability according to usual bituminous road layer construction procedures have been proven to be successful, not increasing the process costs, and giving a good technical and environmental long-term performance. Replicability potential of this CEM is considered of high potential across EU Ms.

FIGURE 1 – CC1 (PORTUGAL). CONSTRUCTION OF PRE-CAST CONCRETES AND ASPHALTS.

FIGURE 2 –WASTE: (LEFT) GREEN LIQUOR DREGS (GLDs); (RIGHT) SLAKER GRITS. NAVIGATOR.

FIGURE 3 – PROCESS: A) GLDs AND GRITS DRYING UP, B) ROAD CONSTRUCTION AFTER MIXING.

FIGURE 4 – APPLICATION: ASPHALT PAVEMENTS FOR INDUSTRIAL USE.

TABLE 1 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE CC1B MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	NAVIGATOR (waste producer), DILUMEX (waste manager), MEGAVIA (Constructor), UAV (scientific partner)
LOCATION	Celulose Bombeiros road, Cacia (Portugal).
WASTE	Slaker Grits (Grits), Green Liquor Dregs (GLDs)
PRODUCT	Asphalt hot mixtures
APPLICATION	Asphalt road pavement

TABLE 2 CC1B ASPHALT PAVEMENT WITH GRITS AND GLDS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Description/fact</i>	<i>Lesson learnt</i>
Wastes (Grits , GLDs)	<p><u>Grits</u>: non-hazardous waste. Ejects from the lime kiln and limestone fragments precipitated during causticizing reactions. Contain sodium and aluminum salts and are strongly alkaline. Low content of elements of concern and low leachability of metals, chloride, fluoride and sulphate. Low contains of Dissolved Organic Carbon (DOC) and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS).</p> <p><u>GLDs</u>: non-hazardous waste. High calcite content, alkaline -high buffering capacity. Low trace elements concentration, not relevant hazardous compounds leaching concerns but some salts. Low hydraulic conductivity.</p>	<p>PPI's causticizing non-hazardous residuals that are currently mainly disposed to landfill (95% of disposal rate).</p> <p>GLDs and Grits are environmentally acceptable for the application, but GLDs content of salts can be excessive. Need salts washing.</p> <p>High humidity (16-40%) on both wastes. Need for drying up before using.</p>

<p>Regulatory framework</p>	<p>EN-13043: aggregates for bituminous mixtures and surface treatments for roads, airfields and other trafficked areas (2002).</p> <p>EN 13108-1: “Bituminous mixtures – Material specifications – Part 1: Asphalt concrete”</p>	<p>Lack of specific and harmonized EU regulation for the use of Grits / GLDs in construction works.</p> <p>These materials are non-hazardous wastes instead by-products or EoW. This fact suppose an important barrier for an easy adoption</p>
<p>Proceedings</p>	<p>The process of GLDs and Grits valorizing may imply a pre-treatment based on drying and sieving. For some GLDs and Grits currents salts removal will be probably necessary also.</p>	<p>The PAPERCHAIN experience only required drying and sieving process.</p> <p>“Extra” process drying can be done by natural energy employing facilities (greenhouse) and machinery for materials occasional removal.</p> <p>New skills and proceedings on Grits/GLDs waste efficient treatment is required to be included in the CEM value chain.</p>
<p>Barriers</p>	<p>Drying, sieving (and washing) process, plus enviromnetal controls can add an important cost to the valorization process.</p> <p>Lack of harmonized and specific regulation of using Grits/GLDs prevent their use.</p> <p>% of substitution of natural filler and aggregates by GLDs is limited.</p>	<p>Aggregates availability and treatment and storage logistics are more complex than standard raw materials (fillers and aggregates) handling.</p> <p>“Low cost” alternatives must be employed for waste treatment.</p>
<p>Enablers</p>	<p>After Grits/GLDs are treated, their use and workability can be similar to standard aggregates.</p>	<p>Standard working equipment for mixtures and road making can be employed after waste treatment. Not needs for a special machinery adaptation for asphalt production.</p>
<p>LCA/CO2 footprint</p>	<p>Throughout 1-year, a visual and performance monitoring was performed. Good mechanical and environmental performance was observed.</p>	<p>The features and characteristics of the targeted construction products were not hindered or modified by the introduction of these wastes after long-term monitoring.</p>

<p>Exploitation</p>	<p>GLDs and Grits landfilling costs as a exploitation driver, where nearly all GLDs and Grits are actually landfilled.</p> <p>The current robust and well-established supply chain of raw materials for the sector is one of the main market entree barriers that the PAPERCHAIN product will have to deal with.</p>	<p>Successful incorporation of Grits / GLDs to bituminous road pavements.</p> <p>Uncertainties about their quality and long-term performance may remain in the sector.</p> <p>Competitive prices are not guaranteed by the new process, as costs from salts removal (for some GLDs), drying and sieving may require a case by case specific detailed evaluation.</p> <p>The main obstacle resides actually in the negotiations with the public administration about the status of waste. The legal use of "waste" material depends on public authorisation that can delay the market uptake of the SRM.</p>
<p>Replicability potential</p>	<p>EU market is huge (close to 280M tonnes produced in 2019) and in an increasing number of countries, reclaimed asphalt and/or demolition waste is reused/recycled to replace virgin aggregates and part of the binder (EAPA, 2019).</p>	<p>Sustainability principles of the Circular Economy Action Plan, as "increasing re-used and recycled content in products, while ensuring their performance and safety" are increasingly adopted by the sector.</p> <p>The adoption of different waste clasification and use regulation strategies across EU is the major constrain for CC1b replication.</p> <p>Apart of waste availability, the use of low carbon footprint and alternative low-cost technologies for GLDs and Grits treatment can vary from MS, and therefore, the economic feasibility and the replication oportunity for this CEM.</p>